

EFFECT OF SINGLE PARENTHOOD ON ADOLESCENT ACHIEVEMENT AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN EDO STATE

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Abstract

This study examines the effect of single parenthood on the achievement of adolescents among secondary school students in Edo State. The study was guided by two hypotheses. The target population was all the students in the 15 public secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area, with senior secondary students SS 3 constituting the actual population. The causal comparative and quasi-experimental research designs were adopted; data were analyzed using mean, standard deviation, two-tailed independent t-test, and analysis of variance. Findings revealed that mean 50.28 (Std. Dev. = 8.091) for the assessment group and 49.68 (Std. Dev. = 9.235) for the control group, with t-value of 0.106 indicates that single parenthood has a significant effect on adolescents' achievement, while 59.41 (Std. Dev. = 8.022) for single parenthood and 49.08 (Std. Dev. = 7.038) for caregiver, with t-value of 0.01 indicates that there is no significant difference in single parenthood/caregivers on adolescents' achievement. The implication of the study is that counselors and para-counselors should be watchful when teaching or counseling students from such homes to help them get the required assistance concerning their school work, redirect their interest, and take their study seriously. The study concluded that understanding the complexities is crucial for developing effective policies and support mechanisms to ensure positive educational outcomes for all students, regardless of family structure, and recommendations were made among others. Counselors should monitor and ensure that students from single parenthood homes are not left out, and plan timetables for their daily activities to encourage them to do assignments at home. This approach helps maintain focus and motivation, leading to steady progress over time.

Introduction

In recent years, the single parenting phenomenon has increasingly become a global concern. Developed countries, in particular, experience an increase in single-parent families as divorce becomes more common (Materu, 2019).

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The UK has over one million single-parent families, with one in seven being single-parent families (Kigera, 2022). Marsiglio, Amato, and Lamb (2017) added that most single-parent families come into being as a consequence of marital breakdown, separation, or divorce, but the increasing proportions are the result of births out of wedlock. According to the United States Census, the number of children who are dependent and live with only one parent rose every year, causing considerable concern among policymakers and the public (Mrinde, 2014).

Single parenting is a situation in which mothers or fathers raise their children without a spouse (Abel, 2023). There are different reasons why a person becomes a single parent. They may choose this lifestyle or they may have been in a relationship that they left, or perhaps their partners have died or left them (Benokraitis, 2015).

Single-parent families differ from families with two parents living under the same roof. They differ in many ways, but the most common difference is how the parent interacts with the child (McLanahan & Booth, 2014). In dual-parent families, the mother and father usually decide together how to run the household, whereas in single-parent households, issues may be decided with the children. In some single-parent households, members may unrealistically expect that the family can function like a two-parent family and may feel that something is wrong when it cannot (Tessa, 2011).

Lim (2016) argued that single-parent households are more likely to have inferior educational achievements than two-parent households. This is partly because single-parent homes have fewer financial resources and less time for parenting, which can lead to less parental participation in the child's schooling. Moreover, single parents may feel overwhelmed by the responsibility of juggling caring for their children, maintaining a job, and keeping up with the bills and household chores (Adeniyi, 2019). Typically, the family's finances and resources are drastically reduced following the parents' divorce. Single-parent families deal with many other pressures and potential problem areas that the nuclear family does not have to face (Amadu & Moses, 2013).

Fareo (2019) stressed that the source of the problems is not necessarily single-parenthood itself but a combination of economic pressures, family instability, and conflict between parents. For example, a single parent with adequate resources may provide a stable, nurturing home in which children thrive just as well as those who have two parents. Conversely, a single parent who is just scraping by and has little time, energy, or skill for parental duties might have children who are at risk for a variety of problems (Obieke, 2013).

Mupfumira (2017) affirmed that single parents have experienced even greater challenges as they have to be both mothers and fathers to raise their children. In such a situation, a single parent is in one way or another obliged to play the roles of a father and a mother in raising the child, and in many cases, it becomes a problem for the children. It is evident that parents are the first point of contact for children, and when both parents are alive and responsible, the child would derive effective care from the parents, which will enable their growth and development in a good manner. (Ekpenyong & Lawrence, 2016).

Benokraitis (2014) argues that the absence of one parent has serious effects on the child, which consequently influences their educational achievement in school. A relationship exists between parenting and students' academic achievement. Parents play a major role in children's academic achievement because they can influence their child's thinking and learning during their development (Chukwuka, 2018).

According to Abankwa (2013), children from mother-only families have poorer academic achievement. These children are likely to have higher school absentee rates and drop out of school, which may lead to poverty. Furthermore, they are more likely to marry early and to have children at a tender age, both in and out of marriage, to divorce, and to commit delinquent acts such as drug and alcohol usage because they lack a good parenting style for their academic development.

Perhaps, single mothers and fathers do not have as much time as required to fully participate in their children's schooling, thus adding to the problems for children of single-parent families. Therefore, children from single-

parent households face many challenges throughout their growth and academic achievement (Ajila & Olutola, 2012).

Azuka (2013) explains that the family must carry out its duties and responsibilities as the principal educator and moral and character supervisor. In that regard, if a single parent heads the family, it is often very difficult for the single parent to provide the required nurturing for children by the expected moral standards of the particular society. This is due to reasons beyond the patient's biological makeup. In most African cultures, a well-marked social distance exists between males and females. This means that male children would feel more comfortable guided by their fathers, whereas girls would cling to their mothers (Coontz, 2017). Against this backdrop, effect of single parents on secondary school students' academic achievement was studied.

Literature review

Definition of single parenthood

Single parenting is a family arrangement in which one parent lives with and raises one or more children without the presence of another parent. Single mothers, single fathers, and even single grandparents or other relatives may fall into this category. Single parenthood can occur due to several factors, including divorce, the death of a spouse, or desertion. Adoption or artificial insemination are two examples of intentional choices that might result in single parenting.

Challenges Facing Single-Parented Students and the Effects of Challenges on Their Education Attainment

There was a rapid increase in the number of single-parent families in the latter half of the twentieth century. This change has been used by some people to argue that we are witnessing a breakdown of the family, with negative effects on children, families and society (Eur, 2017). Others suggest that single-parent families have been present in all societies over time and should not be viewed as abnormal or problematic but rather as an alternative family form. No matter what people view about the presence of single parent families yet the presence of families headed by one-parent has a major influence on the social, economic and political context of family life as far as education of the children is concern. Due to the fact that Single-parented children face many challenges throughout their development, the challenges and the effect of challenges on their education are raised and discussed as follow:

- i.** Family background is key to student's life in and outside of school. Social economic status of the family is one of the factors that influence students learning. Florence and Edebor (2016) have found in their studies that students who have low social economic status are more likely to score low marks, to drop out of school. Most of single-parent families have a low level of economic power and therefore they cannot provide their children with school requirements like school fees, text books, exercise books and other learning materials. Though some of single parent are rich yet many are poor.
- ii.** Family poverty also can lead to other problems such as diseases, poor school attendance and performance and psychological problems. Myom (2015) comment that for many low-income or single-parent families, the challenges that are mostly faced by children and youths are directly or indirectly related to the poor economic condition for their families, not just to parenting style. Poverty directly reduces the access and quality of resources, social and health services and opportunities such as food, shelter, health care, education, and transportation. Yawe (2011) also maintains that poverty affects the ability of parents to provide consistent supervision and monitoring, adequate family management practices, and a range of social and educational stimulating experiences. Due to less income, single parent children suffer much in getting education resources which make some of them to be the victims of child labour hence they can be dropout or have poor performance and fail to achieve their dreams.
- iii.** The other challenge is lack of discipline at school. Usually good behaviours, appropriate values and attitude of children are moulded by parents as parents are the role models of their children. The children from single parent lack role models as well as supervision from their parents. Due to the absence of one parent income, the remaining

parent is forced to use most of her/his time looking for home needs and as a result the children start misbehaving at home and at school. Natujwa (2014), observe that adolescents in intact families are less likely to exhibit behaviour problems in school and tend to have higher levels of academic achievement. Compared to children living in intact families, peers living in single-mother families or with cohabiting partners are more likely to be suspended or expelled from school; more likely to be engaged in delinquent activities or more likely to have problems getting along with their teachers, doing homework or paying attention in school (Muhle, 2020).

iv. Children growing up in single-parent households are at a great risk of depression that is manifested in chronic and pronounced unhappiness, sexual promiscuity, delinquency in the form of drug abuse, petty stealing, alcoholism and acts of breaking into intense anger, apathy and restlessness. In so doing these students can't concentrate in studies. (Coontz, 2017). Also Chukwuka (2017) assert that single parent students are more likely to use drugs and alcohol with boys raised by single father more affected. Single parents struggle with time management due to double responsibilities; therefore they are less involved with their children, which give less encouragement to their children. Mupfumira, (2017) maintains that the effect of parent involvement in their children has been linked to both negative and positive influence. Parental involvements prevent behaviour problems. Therefore whenever parents are less involved with their children, generally children will involve themselves in the use of alcohol, smoking cigarettes as well as marijuana in order to relieve anxiety and forget their problems.

v. Drug and alcohol abuse: single parent children can commit crime. Mothers who are left alone to raise children use most of their time to look for money and material resources so as to support their families. They have little time for monitoring the family, this leaving a chance and possibility for their children to start misbehaving or committing crime. Moreover, children who are brought up in homes with marital conflicts become angry and quarrelsome, this leading them to commit crime and other antisocial acts. Materu (2019) found in their study that in mother-only families, children tend to experience short and long-term economic and psychological disadvantages: a higher absentee rate at school, lower levels of learning, a higher dropout rate and more delinquent activity. This is caused by lack of monitoring at their homes.

vi. Furthermore children from single-parent families face health problems due to lack of proper care as a result of financial constraints. For example, their parents cannot afford to get balanced diets for their children and thus the latter are easily attacked by diseases. Moreover, the children lack psychological support, which can easily expose them to health problems such as mental problems. Kigera (2022) state that children in single-parent homes are more likely to experience health-related problems as a result of the decline in their living standard, including unbalanced meals, poor shelter and lack of health insurance for medication. Later on, as children from single-parent families become adults, they are more likely to marry early, have children early, and divorce. Girls are at the great risk of becoming single-mothers as a result of non-child-bearing within a marriage or else divorce. According to Abel (2023), children growing up without their own married parents are linked with higher rates of stress, depression, anxiety and low self-esteem during the teenage years, problems that can significantly reduce their ability to focus on classroom work and to achieve in school. Research shows that parental divorce has lasting negative emotional effects throughout childhood, adolescence and adulthood. McInahan, et, al. (2014) also indicates that when one-parent is missing, not only does the remaining one "fight a personal monster" but also the children do battle as well. In single-parent families 30-50 percent of children suffer depression as compared with only 5-10 percent in two-parent homes. Poor school performance, disturbance in social adjustment and eating and sleeping disorders alert the parent that something is wrong. Aggressive behaviour and illness, which are real or imagined, seem to emerge and multiply.

vii. Another challenge that is associated with single parents' children's life is involvement in sexual activities and teen pregnancy. They engage in relationships with friends of the opposite sex to compensate for the missed parental love and joy at their homes. By so doing, they think that they are solving their problems while unfortunately risking themselves to pregnancy and/or sexually transmitted diseases such as HIV/AIDS. Some girls engage in sexual activity so as to get money to support their family and themselves. Lim (2016) comment that adolescent females between the ages of 15 and 19 years, who are reared in homes without fathers, are significantly more likely to engage in premarital sex than adolescent females reared in homes with both a mother and a father. As a result, most of these children either fail in school work or are likely to be expelled from school for such habits. Single-parents have little time to make follow up of their children's academic progress. They are overworked, using most of their time to find money to support their families. They do not have time to talk with the children, checking for their children exercise books or if they are attending school, as a result children academic progress decline. Mrinde (2014) in their study found that family structure is associated with parents' educational expectations and involvement with their children's schoolwork. Children of single or stepparents reported that their parents had lower educational expectations for them compared to reports from children in intact families. The former group also reported that their parents are less likely to monitor school-work and provide less overall supervision of social activities, as compared to reports from children in intact families. On the other hand Adeniyi (2019) state that adolescents from divorced single-parent households tend to have greater levels of absenteeism, tardiness and truancy in school as compared with peers in intact families. Parental divorce alters daily routines and work schedules while imposing additional demands on both adults and children living in single-parent households. Moreover Single-parent students face economic hardship in their homes, leading to inability to get necessary school materials such as school uniforms, school fees, exercise books, bus fare, text books and other school needs. Economic hardship results into other problems like poor nutrition and health problems, leading to failure to attend school. Financial conditions required some adolescents to work part-time. These burdens resulted in children from single-parent households having greater levels of absenteeism, tardiness and truancy in school. There are many factors at school and at home which contribute to poor academic performance of pupils from single-parent families. Such factors include truancy possibly due to lack of school fees and school requirements; health problems associated with poor nutrition; poor concentration in lessons associated with lack of needs; and possible poor image and mistreatment in school which make them fail to pay attention to their teachers. They also lack guidance and follow-up from parents, because many single-parents use most of their time to look for home needs. Benokraitis (2014) argue that parental divorce or separation has a bearing on youths' academic performance and educational expectations.

Apart from poor school attendance and poor academic performance, many students from single-parent families tend to drop out of school due to family poverty. Their parents cannot support their education because they lack money for school fees, school uniforms, bus fare, stationery, textbooks, and other school contributions. In turn, such students are themselves forced to run away from school to look for employment so that they can earn money to help themselves and their families. Benokraitis (2015) pointed out that children from single-parent families are more likely to drop out of school, become delinquent, be poor as adults, divorce, and bear children outside marriage. In general, the literature suggests that children of single parents face many challenges in their lives. The challenges include economic hardship, which leads to missed school requirements. Other challenges include dropping out from school, lack of discipline, engaging in drugs and alcohol abuse, poor attendance at school, sexual activity, teen pregnancy, and poor academic performance due to lack of parental involvement in their studies.

Causes of single parenthood

The causes of single parenthood are complex and multifaceted, often involving a combination of personal choices, life circumstances, and external factors. Support systems and policies that address the needs of single-parent families can play a crucial role in helping them thrive despite the challenges they face.

Here are some common causes of single parenthood:

1. Separation: Divorce or separation is one of the most prevalent reasons for single parenthood. When parents decide to end their relationship, one parent typically becomes the primary caregiver, resulting in a single-parent household. Divorce: This occurs when a couple separates after cohabitation or a marriage, and an ex-spouse has physical custody of the children. Single parenting occurs when a woman gives birth to a child and does not live with the child's father or any other partner, male or female. They maintained that this caused their learning difficulties and academic achievement failure.

2. Divorce is one of the causes of single parenting. This is a serious problem because many single parented students are affected academically. Conversely interviews with teachers produced similar responses to those produced by students. A good number of teachers pointed out that divorce develops a big problem for students in achieving their dreams. For instance, one classroom teacher repeated the following:

It is our responsibility to make the environment safe for students in and outside the classroom. However, the problem of parents' divorce, which results in single parenting, affects student learning psychologically, socially, and emotionally.”

From these findings, divorce, as one of the sources of single parenting, has affected students' academic development. In his study, Kigera (2022) supported the finding that children and youth living with single parents as a result of the increased number of divorce, separation, death, and unmarried women. Furthermore, divorce and separation have added challenges to single-parent students because the remaining parent is concentrating on looking after family needs while forgetting other roles of the parent, such as being a role model, monitoring, supervising, guiding, counseling, and making follow-up on the children's academic progress. Materu (2019) argues that parental divorce or separation has a bearing on the academic performance and educational expectations of youths.

3. Death of a Spouse: The death of a spouse or partner can leave the surviving parent as the sole caregiver of their children. The sudden transition to single parenthood can be emotionally and financially challenging.

4. Choice or Circumstances: Some individuals may choose to become single parents through adoption, donor insemination, or other means. Alternatively, circumstances such as a partner's abandonment or an unplanned pregnancy may result in single parenthood.

5. Unmarried Parenthood: Increasingly, individuals may choose to raise children outside traditional marriage or may become single parents due to the breakdown of a non-marital relationship.

6. Military Service: Deployments and military service can result in one parent being absent for extended periods, effectively making the other parent a single parent.

7. Domestic Violence or Abuse: In situations of domestic violence or abuse, the victimized parent may choose to leave the relationship to protect themselves and their children, resulting in single parenthood.

8. Economic Factors: Economic hardships, unemployment, or financial instability can strain relationships and lead to separation or divorce, thereby contributing to single parenthood.

9. Teenage Parenthood: If the teenage parent decides to raise the child without the support of the other parent or external family members, it can lead to single parenthood.

10. Migration or Mobility: Factors such as migration for work, educational opportunities, or other reasons can sometimes result in one parent being separated from their children, effectively making the remaining parent a single parent.

Effect of Single Parenting on Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement

Obviously, secondary education determines students' future career. Therefore, if children do not have the opportunity to attend secondary education, this may affect their future lives.

However, many children could be unable to attend secondary education because of the inability of their single parents to pay their school fees. Moreover, many children are denied secondary education, which may result in destruction of their lives.

Similarly, thousands of students drop out yearly because their single parents could not take care of their school responsibilities. Yet, many children join bad friends to survive because their single parents lack to meet their needs. However, in rural, urban, and riverine areas in Nigeria, single parents failed to contribute immensely to their children's secondary education. Because many single parents always complain of a shortage of money to take care of their children, secondary education is too difficult for many male and female children under the umbrella of single parents. However, the inability to meet their pre-requisites has led to many problems in their secondary education, forcing them to marry at a premature age. The majority of those who attended secondary schools could not complete their studies because of the financial constraints of being single parents.

Indeed, the poor care of single parents has caused many female children to carry unwanted pregnancies while they are to be in school. Males involve different bad groups such as army robbers, assassins, kidnaping, and theft. For instance, four secondary school students were apprehended for different offenses at Kaduna just recently, while three of them came from single parents. In court, they told the lawyers that the inability of their parents to care for their education made them involved in kidnaping because they believed that once they kidnaped people, it is possible to get money for their schooling (Adeniyi, 2019).

Implication of single parents on the academic performance of students in Nigeria

Obviously, parents serve as pillars for children; moreover, it may be cumbersome for any child to achieve without the proper contributions of the parents. However, only parents can determine how their child's future will be either good or bad. However, in situations where the parental is lacking, especially single parenting, the children will face the following challenges:

Denied of Education: thousands of children have problems of single parenting, which shape their futures. Moreover, the majority of single parents find it difficult to send their children to school because they are facing financial constraints and other relevant challenges that are rampant among single parents in Nigeria. Similarly, many children from single parents drop out of school because of their parents' inability.

Early marriage: Similarly, thousands of teenagers have been married because of the inability of their parents to provide them with a sound education, while many are under bondage of cohabitation because their parents failed to send them to school, although this is common among single-parent children. For instance, in the northern parts of Nigeria, early marriage prevails among teenagers, although some teenagers have a father and mother, but the majority of them are single parents. Similarly, in Yoruba, single parents affected the lives of many children.

Exposure to criminality: Many children have been exposed to criminals because their parents found it difficult to care for them. However, this affects their education in life; however, single parents have contributed much to the inability to give them a sound education. Indeed, many students exposed to bad things lost their lives, while others remained in prison. This is mar to their future, although it is not the fault of many children but the inability of their parents to care for them.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were developed and tested at the 0.05 level of significance:

1. Single parenthood had no significant effect on adolescents' achievement among secondary school students in Edo State who took the examination and those who did not.
2. The difference in single parenthood/caregivers has no significant effect on the achievement of adolescents among secondary school students in Edo State.

Methodology

Given this study's quantitative direction, the causal comparative and quasi-experimental research designs were adopted. The choice of these designs was necessary to demonstrate causality between an intervention and an outcome. The researchers combined both descriptive and quantitative analyses and pre-examination and post-examination test design. Hence, the descriptive design is meant to complement the weakness of the quasi-experimental design, which is an alternative to the randomized experiment with the characteristic of assigning assessment using a cut-off score on the variables. To ensure group equivalent, the homogeneity of the group was tested by selecting two arms each of the same classes in the same school from two schools with similar age, sex, teaching methods, and environment. This step was taken to increase internal validity while the later involved the use of assessment and control groups to compare whether the intervention affected the change in behavior. The results of this step are presented in Table 1.

The target population of the study was all the students in the 15 public secondary schools in Oredo Local Government Area, with senior secondary students SS 3 constituting the actual population. Four intact classes were set using science students and social science arms in each school. A sample of 82 students was purposively drawn from two schools strategically located in the area. These schools were designated as schools A, located in the commercial district of the area, and school B, which is located within the area. The schools were coded for data protection and anonymity. Students were stratified according to being raised by a single parent or caregiver to obtain a representative target population. Simple random sampling was used to obtain the following sample: single parenthood students =20, caregiver students =20 from school A, and single parenthood students =20, caregiver students =22 for school B.

The data obtained were analyzed using the mean, standard deviation, two-tailed independent t-test, and ANOVA. A four-point Likert scale questionnaire titled Post Examination Test Questionnaire (PETQ) was constructed by researchers and validated by independent experts in related fields with test-retest reliability index of .62 established. The instrument comprises two sections. Section a supplies demographic information on the subjects, while section B elicits information from adolescent students in public secondary schools in the Oredo Local Government Area.

Results

Hypothesis One: There is no significant effect of single parenthood on adolescents' achievement among secondary school students in Edo State of those that took the examination assessment from single parent and those that are not.

Table 1: Pre- examination and Post-test Mean and Standard Deviation Scores on Effects of Single Parenthood on Adolescents’ Achievement among Secondary School Students in Edo State

Group	Pre-test			Post-test				
	N	- X	Std. dev.	N	- X	Std. Difference	Dev	
Assessment								
Group	40	32.60	9.68	40	12.42	1.66	20.18	8.02
Control	40	26.97	2.78	40	26.02	1.76	0.95	1.02
Total	80	59.57	12.46	80	38.44	3.42	21.13	9.04

The results of the t-test are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: t-test analysis on the effectiveness of single parenthood on adolescents’ achievement among secondary school students in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State of those that took the examination assessment from single parent and those that are not

Variable (2-tailed)	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	T	Sig
Assessment	22	50.28	8.091	0.106	.020
Control	18	49.68	9.235		

*Significance at $\leq .05$ Sig.

Table 2 shows the results of the t-test analysis on the effect of single parenthood on adolescents’ achievement among secondary school students in Oredo Local Government Area for the assessment and control groups, which showed a mean of 50.28 (SD = 8.091) for the assessment group and 49.68 (SD = 9.235) for the control group, with a t-value of 0.106, which is greater than -05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates that single parenthood has a significant effect on adolescents’ achievement among secondary school students in Oredo Local Government Area of those who took the single-parent examination and those who are not.

Hypothesis Two: Single parenthood/Caregivers have no significant effect on the achievement of adolescents among secondary school students in Edo State.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation Difference on Adolescents’ Achievement among Secondary School Students in Edo State

Test	N	Mean	Std. Dev
Single parenthood	22	22.08	2.16
Caregiver	18	21.98	2.08

The t-test results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: t-test analysis of single parenthood/caregiver difference in adolescents' achievement among secondary school students in Edo State after examination assessment

Variable	N	X	Std. Dev.	t-value	Sig.(2-tailed)
Single Parenthood	22	59.41	8.022	.001	0.036
Caregiver	18	49.08	7.038		

*Significance at ≤ 0.05 Sig.

Table 4 presents the single parenthood/caregiver difference in adolescent achievement among secondary school students in Edo State after an assessment test of 59.41 (Std. Dev. = 8.022) for single parenthood and 49.08 (Std. Dev. = 7.038) for caregiver, with a t-value of 0.01 which is less than the 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis is upheld. This indicates that there is no significant difference in the achievement of single parents/caregivers among secondary school students in Edo State who took the examination assessment in Oredo Local Government Area of Edo State.

Discussion

Single Parenthood was found to have effects on the achievement of adolescents. The pre-examination test mean score and standard deviation for the assessment group were 32.60 and 9.68, respectively, whereas the post-examination test mean score was 12.42 and 1.66, respectively. The mean score and standard deviation for the control group were 26.97 and 2.78 at pre-examination test and 26.02 and 1.76, respectively.

The difference of 20.18 and 8.02 for the assessment group showed a positive improvement in the achievement scores of the group, whereas the control group did not show any difference. Therefore, the assessment group was affected by single parenthood upbringing. This finding disagrees with those of Tenibiaje and Tenibiaje (2011), who found no correlation or relationship between the type of home through which a student comes from and his/her academic performance in the school. This study is also in line with the views of Shim and Finch (2014), who found that single parents' students perform poorly in classroom participation compared to intact parents. The implication of this is that students from deserted homes will find it difficult to ask, answer questions, and concentrate due to their condition. Therefore, counselors and para-counselors should be watchful when teaching or counseling students from deserted homes to help them make contributions in class discussions and take their study seriously.

With regard to single parenthood/caregivers, the results showed that adolescents' achievement is greatly affected by single parenthood/caregivers, and there is no difference in the performance of students from single parenthood non-caregivers. This is consistent with the finding of Natujwa (2014) that adolescents from single-parent homes and caregiver homes perform below average in their academic achievement compared with those from homes where both parents are intact. The implication of this is that single parent and caregiver students find it difficult to obtain the required assistance concerning their school work, either because they are busy or are not interested. Therefore, counselors and teachers of such students should redirect their interest and confidence to the purpose of learning that will restore self-determination for better academic improvement.

Conclusion

The study found that single parenthood affects students' academic performance as students from single-parent households may perform slightly lower academically on average compared to those from two-parent households, depending on factors such as socioeconomic status and parental involvement. This eventually plays out in the

quality of the parent-student relationship, access to resources such as educational support, home environment stability, and the resilience and adaptability of the family unit, which play crucial roles in determining adolescent academic achievement. Furthermore, while there may be some correlation between single parenthood and adolescent academic performance, the overall impact is nuanced and influenced by various factors. Understanding these complexities is crucial for developing effective policies and support mechanisms to ensure positive educational outcomes for all students, regardless of family structure.

Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. Students of single parenthood should be encouraged to seek academic support by taking advantage of resources offered by your school or community, such as tutoring services, study groups, or after-school programs. These can provide additional help and guidance in challenging subjects that can lead to overall academic improvement.
2. Counselors and para-counselors should monitor and monitor school activities so that students from single parenthood homes are not left out. They should also plan a timetable for their daily activities to enable them to do assignments at home. This approach helps maintain focus and motivation, leading to steady progress over time.

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